

Graphical Abstract

Multimodal GeoAI: An Integrated Spatio-Temporal Topic-Sentiment Model for the Analysis of Geo-social Media Posts for Disaster Management

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Highlights

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- We present an integrated, multimodal Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI) model for geo-social media analysis capable of clustering posts such that they have (1) a distinct semantic topic, (2) an associated sentiment, (3) a geographic location/bounds and (4) a temporal reference.
- To cluster multimodal feature vectors, we introduce the Geographic Growing Self-Organising Map (Geo-GSOM), a dynamic and spatially explicit Self-Organising Map (SOM) variant that learns a neuron grid which can be interpreted in geographic space.
- In quantitative experiments across several data sets, our integrated GeoAI approach outperformed a comparable state-of-the-art sequential workflow regarding semantic topic quality and sentiment uniformity while maintaining similar spatial and temporal variance.
- In a case study regarding the 2021 Ahr Valley floods in Western Germany, we demonstrate that our approach can provide valuable insights for disaster management by extracting interpretable multimodal information.

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David Hanny^{a,b}, Bernd Resch^{a,b,c}

^a*Interdisciplinary Transformation University Austria, Linz, Austria*

^b*Department of Geoinformatics, Paris Lodron University of Salzburg, Salzburg, Austria*

^c*Center for Geographic Analysis, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA, USA*

Abstract

The analysis of online communication on social networks has become a central research interest to improve disaster management. Especially geo-referenced textual posts have been investigated extensively using techniques from Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI), topic modelling and sentiment analysis. However, workflows are traditionally sequential with independent processing steps, limiting their ability to capture interconnections between modalities and risking chains of dependencies. To overcome these limitations, we introduce an integrated GeoAI model called the Joint Spatio-Temporal Topic-Sentiment (JSTTS) model. Our proposed method combines semantic, sentiment, spatial and temporal knowledge into continuous feature vectors and is capable of computing geographically delineated sentiment-associated clusters of topics with meaningful location and temporal information. The properties of the JSTTS model were validated experimentally and the approach was evaluated against a comparable sequential workflow. Overall, our JSTTS model achieved higher topic quality scores with an average of 0.145 compared to 0.034 for the sequential workflow and higher average sentiment uniformity with an average of 0.89 versus 0.73. At the same time, both approaches exhibited similar spatial and temporal variance. As a secondary result, the Geographic Growing Self-Organising Map (Geo-GSOM) was developed to cluster multimodal feature vectors meaningfully in geographic space. It was evaluated on artificial training data where it reproduced up to 90% of the spatial autocorrelation while the non-spatial Growing Self-Organising Map (GSOM) only achieved 55%. The learned neuron grid can also be interpreted geographically. The utility of the JSTTS approach is demonstrated through

a case study on the 2021 Ahr Valley flooding in Western Germany, where it identified interpretable multimodal clusters, a subset of which proved relevant for disaster management. The approach can be extended to other use cases and adapted for different modalities, holding potential for numerous follow-up studies.

Keywords:

geoAI, machine learning, disaster management, social media, natural language processing

1. Introduction

Fuelled by billions of active users, the analysis of online social networks has become an integral field of research in computational and social sciences. The massive amounts of data available on these platforms provide an opportunity for insights into societal patterns, relationships, and events. A fraction of social media posts comes with an additional spatial reference laying the foundation for research efforts in Geographic Information (GI) Science to discover geospatial patterns. Roick and Heuser (2013) shaped the term of Location-Based Social Networks (LBSNs) emphasising their potential for analysing human behaviour, location inference or extracting relevant information for tasks like disaster response and disease control.

Of the social media platforms available, micro blogs, where users mainly post short-form textual content with public visibility, such as X (formerly Twitter) or Weibo have been the dominating data sources of LBSN research. Particularly, geo-referenced Twitter data has been used to model, analyse or monitor a variety of phenomena such as earthquakes (Crooks et al., 2013; Resch et al., 2018), floodings (Huang et al., 2018; Lwin et al., 2015), refugee movements (Havas and Resch, 2021) or disease outbreaks (Havas et al., 2021; Stolerman et al., 2023; Wakamiya et al., 2018). Twitter and Weibo are the data sources for 70% of studies in the field (McKittrick et al., 2023). Partly, this can be attributed to the accessibility of posts on these platforms and the relatively simple access via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). Although the fraction of tweets with an explicit geo-location is small, the generally large quantity of posts still allows for the collection of vast enough data sets to conduct meaningful spatial analysis involving statistically robust data sets (Sloan and Morgan, 2015; Serere et al., 2023).

Geo- and time-referenced social media posts can be analysed through

spatio-temporal attributes, content analysis or network analysis. This work focuses on spatio-temporal content analysis of individual posts, where textual data has been extensively studied. Numerous research efforts have applied topic modelling to uncover semantic topics in such data sets (e.g. Resch et al., 2018; Yao and Wang, 2020). Sentiment analysis is also frequently employed to detect the emotional association of posts (e.g. Kovacs-Györi et al., 2018; Camacho et al., 2021). However, the discovered topics are rarely contextualised with other modalities. While extensions of Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et al., 2003) have been proposed to incorporate sentiment (e.g. Lin and He, 2009), space (e.g. Yin et al., 2011) or time (e.g. Blei and Lafferty, 2006), they typically focus on the integration of one or two modalities at a time.

As a result, existing approaches for analysing textual geo-social media data across two or more modalities often rely on sequential workflows, consisting of independent semantic analysis and sentiment classification followed by spatial or spatio-temporal analysis (e.g. AlAgha, 2021; Kwon et al., 2023). While these methods have demonstrated their utility in various applications, they may overlook potential interdependencies between modalities such as the spatial association of topics and sentiments. Moreover, the sequential nature of these workflows can introduce dependencies between processing steps which may affect the consistency and overall quality of the results, particularly when the order of the analysis is varied.

These limitations can be especially problematic in time-sensitive scenarios such as natural disaster management. For instance, consider a flood event where affected citizens use social media to report their conditions. Some posts might describe rising water levels and road closures, while others convey fear, confusion or urgent requests for help. Analysing these posts sequentially by first extracting topics, then detecting sentiments and finally visualising the results in geographic space and time risks missing the interplay between these dimensions. Consequently, important insights about where and when people are discussing specific issues and how they feel about them may be lost.

To address these limitations, we present a novel Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI) approach called the Joint Spatio-Temporal Topic-Sentiment (JSTTS) model. Our method overcomes the constraints of sequential workflows by clustering posts across all four modalities – semantics, sentiment, space and time – simultaneously. Unlike traditional methods, which treat each aspect in isolation, our JSTTS model uses neural networks to compute multimodal clusters of continuous feature vectors. This integrated ap-

proach allows for the consideration of interdependencies between dimensions throughout the clustering process. To maintain spatial coherence during clustering and to overcome the need for a pre-defined number of clusters, our method utilises a customised neural network algorithm called the Geographic Growing Self-Organising Map (Geo-GSOM). It represents a dynamically growing, spatially explicit Self-Organising Map (SOM) variant. The output of our JSTTS model consists of clusters with a distinct semantic topic, an associated sentiment, a geographic location and a temporal reference, providing comprehensive insights into social media content. It can be flexibly parametrised to individually emphasise certain modalities. To showcase the JSTTS model’s capabilities, we compare it to a state-of-the-art sequential analysis workflow as typically used in previous studies. Furthermore, we evaluate the quality of the Geo-GSOM algorithm for clustering separately and examine how different parametrisations affect the results of our approach.

Our method was designed to be especially valuable in disaster management. During emergency situations caused by natural hazards such as floods, geo-social media provides multimodal information from affected populations which can improve situational awareness for emergency responders. In a case study on the 2021 Ahr Valley floods in Western Germany, we demonstrate how geographically fine-grained multimodal clusters of social media posts align with the impacts of the event. Our JSTTS model is thus a step forward in integrating social media analysis for disaster response efforts.

Overall, the core contributions of this paper can be summarised as follows:

- We introduce the JSTTS GeoAI model for the unsupervised discovery of multimodal clusters in geo-referenced social media posts consisting of (1) a distinct semantic topic, (2) an associated sentiment, (3) a geographic location/bounds and a (4) temporal reference.
- As part of the model, we present the Geo-GSOM neural network algorithm which grows a dynamic neuron grid based on the topology of the data, learns a meaningful representative location for each neuron and can be interpreted in geographic space.
- We quantitatively compare the Geo-GSOM against the non-spatial equivalent Growing Self-Organising Map (GSOM), examine the parametrisation effects for the JSTTS model and compare our JSTTS approach to a state-of-the-art sequential workflow.

- In a case study on the 2021 Ahr Valley floods in Western Germany, we demonstrate how multimodal clusters of social media posts align with the impacts of the event, highlighting the potential of the JSTTS model for improving situational awareness in disaster management.

2. Related Work

Advancements in topic modelling, sentiment analysis and their spatio-temporal extensions in the context of social media can be considered the most relevant previous work for this study. Moreover, our paper touches upon social media analysis for disaster management.

2.1. Topic Modelling

Topic modelling is a technique used for discovering latent semantic topics present in a large collection of documents. It can be depicted as a variant of content analysis for text, assigning one or more "topic codes" to each document (Hoyle et al., 2022). One of the most significant contributions in the field was made with LDA by Blei et al. (2003). The generative idea of LDA has been adapted to include a variety of characteristics such as sentiments (Lin and He, 2009), time (Blei et al., 2003) or social media users (Zhao et al., 2011). However, LDA relies on the bag-of-words assumption where the relationship between the individual words occurring in a document is not captured. Due to this limitation, new embedding-based topic modelling techniques have recently emerged. Dieng et al. (2020) presented the Embedded Topic Model (ETM) which combines the generative idea of LDA with pre-trained embeddings of words and sentences. Sia et al. (2020) showed that clustering high-dimensional semantic embedding vectors can be a powerful topic modelling strategy performing similarly to LDA. The idea of clustering embedding vectors was developed further by Angelov (2020) who proposed top2vec powered by doc2vec, Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) and Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN). Grootendorst (2022) improved this technique and introduced BERTopic which consistently outperformed traditional LDA and top2vec.

Contribution beyond SotA

Although topic models are a powerful tool for analysing large collections of documents, they neglect contextual features like sentiment, geographic location and time present in textual geo-social media posts. Our proposed JSTTS model integrates these dimensions into the topic modelling process, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of the topics.

2.2. Joint Topic-Sentiment Modelling

Joint modelling of topics and sentiments aims to discover not only semantic topics but topics under sentiments or topic-sentiment pairs given a collection of documents. Most previous joint topic-sentiment models (e.g. Fu et al., 2016; Lin and He, 2009; Liang et al., 2023; Dermouche et al., 2015) leverage the generative idea of LDA in a similar fashion, though newer embedding-based techniques have also been proposed.

Taking LDA as the underlying base model, Lin and He (2009) included an additional sentiment layer between the document and the topic layer leading to a model called Joint Sentiment/Topic (JST) model. JST associates sentiment labels with topics, topics with sentiment labels, and words with both sentiment labels and topics. The distributions of sentiments, topics, and words conditioned on topics and sentiments are inferred from the training data. Given that the inference mechanism of JST still relies on word co-occurrences, the output might not be satisfactory if the training corpus is short and small. Fu et al. (2016) addressed this weakness by introducing word embeddings such as word2vec (Mikolov et al., 2013) or FastText (Bojanowski et al., 2017) resulting in the Topic Sentiment Joint Model with Word Embeddings (TSWE). The model extends JST with a word embedding component that includes additional semantic and syntactic information. Dermouche et al. (2015) introduced a similar model that can produce different topic descriptions for different sentiment polarities and returns a sentiment distribution for each topic instead of a hard assignment. Liang et al. (2023) further adapted the JST approach for online reviews and ratings. Hanny and Resch (2024) presented a clustering-based approach for joint topic-sentiment modelling based on semantic embedding vectors and sentiment probabilities which outperformed previous topic-sentiment models in terms of semantic topic quality and sentiment classification accuracy.

Contribution beyond SotA

Even though geographic coordinates and time offer essential real-world context in geo-social media analysis, existing joint topic-sentiment models do not yet include these components. The proposed JSTTS method builds upon the idea of clustering-based topic-sentiment modelling and extends it to generate sentiment-associated topics that can be situated in both geographic space and time.

2.3. Spatial and Temporal Topic Modelling

There has been a fair amount of research output regarding spatial, temporal, and spatio-temporal topic modelling in recent years. Yin et al. (2011) introduced Latent Geographical Topic Analysis (LGTA) for discovering geographic topics from Global Positioning System (GPS)-associated documents and defined a geographic topic as a "spatially coherent meaningful theme" (Yin et al., 2011, p. 248). The LGTA model is based on Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (PLSA) but assumes that topics are generated from regions and not documents. Hong et al. (2012) extended this idea and proposed a generative model that also accounts for user mobility. Time is considered in the Dynamic Topic Model (DTM) introduced by Blei and Lafferty (2006) as extensions of LDA. ETM was adapted in a similar way (Dieng et al., 2019). Grootendorst (2022) also implemented dynamic topic modelling by introducing a time component in the keyword extraction process of BERTopic.

Jointly considering space and time, Hu et al. (2013) developed the probabilistic Spatio-Temporal Topic (STT) model to capture spatio-temporal patterns of social media users. Yuan et al. (2013) proposed the W^4 model (short for Who+Where+When+What) to analyse the spatio-temporal activities of Twitter users. A similar approach was taken by Liu et al. (2015) to predict check-ins, i.e. the presence of the user, at points of interest. Overall, even though numerous research efforts have investigated combined spatio-temporal semantic topic modelling, the working principles of most spatial and temporal topic models are confined to extensions of LDA and PLSA.

Contribution beyond SotA

Clustering-based topic models have not yet been extended to include geographic space and time, even though they have been shown to significantly outperform LDA and PLSA (e.g. Grootendorst, 2022). Our JSTTS approach makes a first step in integrating these modalities and additionally incorporates sentiments, offering a more comprehensive and context-aware understanding of topics.

2.4. Combined Spatio-temporal Semantic and Sentiment Analysis

Spatio-temporal, semantic and sentiment analysis of social media posts has been combined in a variety of different contexts. Camacho et al. (2021) integrated different methods of sentiment classification with spatial clustering methods and spatial statistics to examine geocoded tweets and detect public opinion. Paul et al. (2017) followed a similar approach for spatio-temporal sentiment analysis of tweets concerning the United States of America (USA) presidential election in 2016. Kovacs-Györi et al. (2018) leveraged sentiment analysis and spatio-temporal analysis to extract spatial and temporal patterns of park visits. As a natural limitation of spatio-temporal sentiment analysis, semantics are only considered as part of the filtering process and to the degree of emotional association. It therefore remains unknown what the discovered patterns are truly about. Parimala et al. (2021) presented an algorithm for risk assessment after and during disasters using social media data. It combines sentiment classification powered by a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network trained for semantic classification with spatial and temporal analyses to predict the severity of the disaster. However, the method requires the training of a semantic classification model for the respective disaster and is restricted to the English language. Hu et al. (2020) performed spatial and temporal sentiment analysis of geo-referenced tweets from January to December 2016, focusing on time series and spatial cluster analysis. Subsequently, they applied LDA on top of the positively associated tweets to better understand related semantic dynamics in geographic space.

AlAgha (2021) performed topic modelling using author-pooled LDA in combination with sentiment analysis on tweets regarding the COroNaVirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. The two analyses were carried out independently and spatial analysis was conducted at the country level. Dahal et al. (2019) performed a similar study for tweets related to climate change.

They used keyword-filtered and geotagged posts which were used as input to an LDA topic model and sentiment classification. Subsequently, country- and county-level spatial analysis was conducted along with time series analysis. Similarly, Kwon et al. (2023) proposed a workflow combining LDA-based topic modelling with sentiment analysis and spatial time series analysis, particularly focusing on the comparison of topic-wise sentiment time series among different areas in the USA during the 2016 presidential debates. Zhu et al. (2020) examined the spatio-temporal dynamics of positive sentiment present in COVID-19-related Weibo posts based on sub-topics computed using LDA. Li et al. (2022) implemented a likewise workflow to analyse the public opinion towards COVID-19 vaccines in China from January 2020 to September 2021 using a sequential combination of topic modelling, sentiment analysis and subsequent spatio-temporal analysis.

Contribution beyond SotA

Existing methodologies for spatio-temporal semantic and sentiment analysis typically process semantics and sentiment separately or sequentially. Such approaches have been proven effective in various contexts. However, they can produce fragmented insights or results sensitive to the order of processing steps which limits their suitability for scenarios that require a comprehensive overview. Our method complements these efforts by jointly analysing semantics, sentiment, space and time within a unified framework. By simultaneously considering interdependencies among all modalities, our approach aims to provide more coherent multimodal clusters, thereby offering additional insights beyond those available during sequential or isolated analyses.

2.5. Social Media Analysis for Disaster Management

Social media analysis in multiple modalities holds significant potential to aid disaster management. Wang and Ye (2018) highlighted the multi-dimensional nature of social media data which consists of *content*, *space*, *time* and *network*. Together, these dimensions can provide increased situational awareness. However, with increasing dimensionality, the number of previous studies addressing all these dimensions simultaneously decreases (e.g. Kryvasheyev et al., 2016; Hara, 2015; Wang and Ye, 2018).

Focusing on posting location, time and content, Han et al. (2024) proposed a Time-Geographic-Semantic (TGS) cube to capture the spatio-temporal

semantic behaviour of social media users in emergency situations. Similarly, Dunkel et al. (2019) studied the collective reaction to events on LBSNs and characterised them according to the dimensions *space*, *time*, *theme* and *interlinkage* with the help of an event-reaction-hypercube. However, such representations still require an encoding of the content during pre-processing which is often achieved using topic modelling (as in Han et al., 2024; Dunkel et al., 2019). This limitation is also evident in other studies. Steiger et al. (2016) tackled the problem of discovering spatio-temporal semantic clusters of tweets by combining LDA and a hierarchical Geographic Self-Organising Map (Geo-SOM). Resch et al. (2018) used LDA for extracting earthquake- and damage-related tweets regarding the 2014 Napa earthquake in the USA and followed this step with hot spot analysis to identify earthquake footprints. Ghosh and Guha (2013) utilised a likewise workflow that leveraged LDA to identify obesity-related tweets which were used as input for further geographic analyses. In all of these studies, even though the multimodal nature of social media data was addressed, content analysis was conducted separately from spatial and temporal analysis.

Several studies also looked at posting behaviour during and after disasters. Resch et al. (2018) found that the number of posted tweets per minute peaked during the night of the 2014 Napa earthquake in the larger Bay area in the USA. Similarly, Neppalli et al. (2017) observed a high of storm-related tweets two days from the onset of the 2012 Hurricane Sandy. They also found that positive and negative sentiments clustered more than regularly after the storm’s maximum impact. Negative sentiments were specifically observed more closely to the Hurricane. Gruebner et al. (2018) conducted a likewise study and also performed sentiment analysis for about a million tweets regarding Hurricane Sandy. Based on this data, they calculated discomfort rates for census tracts in New York and found bundled negative sentiments and discomfort after the storm. Furthermore, they observed a positive association of pre-, peri- and post-disaster discomfort. Lee and Yu (2020) examined the impact of language on social media platforms by analysing tweets from the 2013 Colorado floods and found that a concrete language style increased the likelihood of sharing.

Contribution beyond SotA

While previous methodologies in social media analysis for disaster management combine semantic content, sentiment, spatial location and temporal information, they typically rely on sequential or independent workflows. To date, unified approaches that integrate all four modalities simultaneously – *what* people post, *how* they feel, *where*, and *when* – remain limited. Our proposed approach addresses this gap by enabling the simultaneous analysis of semantics, sentiment, space and time within a unified clustering framework. This joint analysis facilitates even more comprehensive insights and can enhance situational awareness beyond conventional methods.

3. Methodology

This study introduces a novel GeoAI model for joint spatio-temporal topic-sentiment analysis called the Joint Spatio-Temporal Topic-Sentiment (JSTTS) model. It was designed for the unsupervised analysis of collections of geo-referenced short-form textual data. The underlying approach follows a three-step procedure: (1) feature engineering in multiple modalities, (2) spatial clustering, and (3) information extraction. First, joint feature vectors representing the semantics, sentiments, location and time of each post are created using transformer-based language models. These feature vectors are then clustered using a geospatially-aware variant of the GSOM (Alahakoon et al., 2000) called the Geo-GSOM and finally, contextual cluster information like the semantic keywords, a summarising cluster label, the overall sentiment, location and time are extracted.

The methodological workflow is depicted in Fig. 1. Going further, input data $d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n, n \in \mathbb{N}$ is assumed where each data point $d_i, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ represents a social media post with textual information, geographic location in the form of a latitude/longitude coordinate or a bounding box and a timestamp.

3.1. Feature Engineering

The goal of the feature engineering process is to obtain a feature vector for each input text such that it is represented in some continuous space and can be processed with common data science methods. In the case of the JSTTS model, the feature space represents a multimodal spatio-temporal

Figure 1: Overview of the presented JSTTS model. Given the input documents, joint feature vectors are built which are clustered in geographic space and finally, contextualised information is extracted.

topic-sentiment space that captures semantics, sentiments, space and time simultaneously, similarly to the idea of a semantic space as proposed by Deerwester et al. (1990) or Angelov (2020). Documents that are similar are close in the multimodal space and documents that are different are further apart.

3.1.1. Pre-processing

To extract semantic and sentiment information, the text of each document is pre-processed by replacing user references and links with standardised tokens (“@user” and “http”) as they convey no relevant semantic information. Pota et al. (2021) found that this can be beneficial for sentiment classification. Moreover, excessive whitespace is stripped as it is not considered during the tokenisation of the language models used.

The geographic location of each post is assumed to be a latitude/longitude coordinate or a bounding box. In case only a bounding box is available, the location is pre-processed by converting it to a point coordinate. This could either happen by computing the centroid or by sampling a point from the bounding box randomly or based on known factors such as population density. While the first method is computationally simpler, it implies the assumption that posts with the same bounding box location were all posted

from exactly the same coordinates.

3.1.2. Information Representation

Next, multimodal feature vectors are created. This section discusses how its individual components are computed.

Semantics. The input feature representing the semantic information derived from the text is extracted by computing a five-dimensional vector representation for each text. It is achieved by first computing a high-dimensional vector representation using Sentence-BERT (SBERT) (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) and reducing it to a lower-dimensional representation using UMAP (McInnes et al., 2020). The number of embedding dimensions was set to five because (1) five-dimensional semantic vectors have successfully been employed for topic modelling purposes (e.g. Angelov, 2020; Groentendorst, 2022) and (2) Allaoui et al. (2020) found that applying UMAP as a pre-processing step significantly improved clustering results for multiple clustering techniques and image data sets. Since the entries of the reduced embedding vectors do not have a fixed range of values, the importance of semantics in the final feature vector can be skewed. The reduced semantic vectors are therefore scaled to unit length by dividing each vector by its norm resulting in a maximum absolute value of one for each entry (Strang, 2016).

Sentiments. For the computation of the sentiment part of the feature vector, we use a multi-class sentiment classification model based on Robustly Optimized BERT Approach (RoBERTa) (Liu et al., 2019). Specifically, the twitter-RoBERTa-base-sentiment by Loureiro et al. (2022) for English-only texts and twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-base-sentiment by Barbieri et al. (2022) for multilingual texts. Both models were pre-trained on large corpora of Twitter data and yield a probability distribution over the classes *negative*, *neutral* and *positive* as the prediction. The three sentiment probabilities are taken as a continuous representation of the inherent sentiment distribution of each respective input text.

Location. After the pre-processing, the geographic location of each post is assumed to be a latitude/longitude coordinate. Each coordinate is projected onto a plane using an equidistant map projection based on the study area that preserves distances between points (Maling, 1992). The projected two-dimensional coordinates are then scaled to a range of $[0, 1]$ in each dimension using a ratio-preserving minimum-maximum transformation to achieve a normalised representation within the value range of the other features. This is done to prevent skew from large values resulting from the projection during

the subsequent clustering step.

Time. Time is processed similarly to coordinates. It is converted to Unix-time (Reingold and Dershowitz, 2018) and also scaled to a range of $[0, 1]$ using a minimum-maximum transformation to achieve a normalised representation.

3.1.3. Vector Creation

Finally, the normalised coordinates, the semantic vector, the sentiment probabilities, and the normalised time are concatenated to obtain a feature vector of the form $[x, y, e_1, \dots, e_5, s_1, \dots, s_3, t]^T$ where x, y denote the projected and scaled coordinates, $e_i, i \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ the semantic dimensions, $s_i, i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ the sentiment dimensions and t the normalised time. The different parts of the vector can be weighted to provide the user control over the importance of the individual features. Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ be scalar values. α is the weight of the geographic components of the feature vector, β is the weight of the sentiment components, and γ is the weight of the time.

3.2. Spatial Clustering

To obtain multimodal collections of posts, a dynamic and spatially-aware SOM variant called the Geo-GSOM is employed. It combines the dynamic nature of the GSOM (Alahakoon et al., 2000) with the spatial properties of the Geo-SOM (Baç¸ao et al., 2005). As opposed to other clustering approaches such as k -means (MacQueen, 1967), hierarchical agglomerative clustering (Ward, 1963), DBSCAN (Ester et al., 1996) or HDBSCAN (Campello et al., 2013), it (1) preserves spatial neighbourhoods, (2) provides additional information that can be visualised using a U-matrix-style representation (Ultsch and Siemon, 1990) or other plots taking into account the neural network’s structure and weights, (3) grows naturally in the number of neurons with a degree of control using spread parameters and (4) preserves the topology of the data in the learned neuron grid. These properties make the proposed approach highly suitable for our research on spatially explicit multimodal analysis. The exact Geo-GSOM algorithm is explained in this section. It consists of four phases: (1) an initialisation phase, (2) a growing phase, (3) a non-geographic smoothing phase and (4) a geographic smoothing phase.

3.2.1. Initialisation Phase

The Geo-GSOM network starts out with four neurons which are initialised randomly except for the geographic components of the weight vectors which

are set to represent the boundaries of the normalised coordinate space. Let x_{\max} and y_{\max} are the maximum coordinate values of the input data points. The four starting neurons are then initialised as in Fig. 2. Given the feature engineering process, zero is assumed to be the minimum coordinate value for both dimensions.

Figure 2: Initial weight vectors of the four starting neurons of a Geo-GSOM network.

In the initialisation phase, the growth threshold GT is also computed which controls how fast the neuron grid grows. It takes three parameters, namely the spread factor SF , the number of input data points n and a spread constant c , and can be written as in Eq. 1. This definition was chosen such that the growth of the network is normalised by the number of feature dimensions D and the number of input data points n . The constant c allows for coarse adjustments of the growth speed while SF provides a more fine-grained variable of control.

$$GT = -D \cdot \ln(SF) \cdot \frac{n}{c} \quad (1)$$

3.2.2. Growing Phase

The growing phase of the Geo-GSOM was inspired by the original algorithm by Alahakoon et al. (2000) but modified to account for geospatial properties. A major caveat of the classic GSOM algorithm for spatial data is that it grows outwards. As a result, geographic weights can potentially increase indefinitely, leaving the vicinity of the original data. Moreover, directions are not preserved due to the uncontrollable growing process.

Thus, to account for spatial structure, the search for the Best Matching Unit (BMU) in the neuron grid is conducted hierarchically, similarly to what would happen in a Geo-SOM (Bação et al., 2004). The geographically closest unit is computed, and subsequently, all nearby neurons within a specified

radius r_{geo} (the geographic tolerance) are considered candidates for the actual BMU computation. Once the BMU has been found, only the non-geographic parts of the weight vectors are updated. Whenever a new node is added to the network, the geographic weights are re-distributed evenly over the network structure such that the leftmost nodes have a value of 0 in the dimension representing the learned x -coordinate and the rightmost nodes have a value of x_{max} . The same principle is applied to the y -dimension of the weight vectors. This way, the neuron grid stays geographically coherent at all times and the network grows *inwards* in space instead of outwards. Formally, one growing iteration τ can be summarised as in Alg. 1.

If new neurons are grown, their weights are computed using Eq. 2 if the BMU has another neighbouring neuron and Eq. 3 if the neuron is grown in between the BMU and another neuron.

$$\vec{w}_{\text{new}} = 2 \cdot \vec{w}_{\text{BMU}} - \vec{w}_{\text{other}} \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{w}_{\text{new}} = \frac{\vec{w}_{\text{BMU}} + \vec{w}_{\text{other}}}{2} \quad (3)$$

To prevent obscure initial weights beyond the value range of the training data, the weight vector entries of each new node are clipped if they exceed an absolute value of 1. After each iteration, the neighbourhood radius is updated using the decaying formula in Eq. 4 where \mathcal{T} is the total number of iterations and the learning rate is updated based on the number of nodes in the network as in Eq. 5. $A, A' \in \mathbb{R}$ are constants for which the respective default values are $A = 0.9$ and $A' = 3.8$ (or, more generally, a number slightly < 4).

$$r^{(\tau)} = r^{(0)} \cdot e^{-\frac{\tau}{\mathcal{T} \cdot \ln(r^{(0)})}} \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha^{(\tau)} = A \cdot \alpha^{(\tau-1)} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{A'}{\#\text{nodes}}\right) \quad (5)$$

3.2.3. Non-Geographic Smoothing Phase

After the growing phase, a smoothing phase is carried out where no new neurons are grown. The geographic weights stay fixed and the non-geographic parts of the weight vectors are adapted analogously to the growing phase such that the quantisation error is minimized.

Algorithm 1 Algorithmic description of one Geo-GSOM *growing* iteration. τ is the current iteration, and \mathcal{W} is the set of all weight vectors. The superscript (geo) denotes the geographic part of a vector in the feature space, and (ngf) the non-geographic part.

Require: input data $\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n$, growth threshold GT , learning rate $\alpha^{(\tau)}$, neighborhood radius $r^{(\tau)}$, geographic tolerance r_{geo} , factor of distribution γ , maximum coordinate values $x_{\text{max}}, y_{\text{max}}$

- 1: **for** $\ell = 1$ to n **do**
- 2: For all weight vectors $\vec{w}_i \in \mathcal{W}$, compute the Euclidian distance between $\vec{p}_\ell^{(\text{geo})}$ and $\vec{w}_i^{(\text{geo})}$ and find the geographic BMU (BMU_{geo}).
- 3: Select a (sub)set $\mathcal{W}_{\text{winner}}$ of weights such that the Chebyshev distance in the neuron structure between BMU_{geo} and each weight is $\leq r_{\text{geo}}$.
- 4: For all $\vec{w}_i \in \mathcal{W}_{\text{winner}}$, compute the Euclidian distance between \vec{p}_ℓ and \vec{w}_i and find the BMU among the subset.
- 5: Update each neuron i with weight \vec{w}_i using the formula

$$\vec{w}_i^{(\text{ngf})} = \vec{w}_i^{(\text{ngf})} + \alpha^{(\tau)} \cdot N(\text{BMU}, i, r^{(\tau)}) \cdot (\vec{p}_\ell^{(\text{ngf})} - \vec{w}_i^{(\text{ngf})})$$

where N is a Gaussian neighbourhood function.

- 6: Increase the total error TE_{BMU} of the BMU by $\|\vec{p}_\ell - \vec{w}_{\text{BMU}}\|_2$.
 - 7: **if** $TE_{\text{BMU}} > GT$ **then**
 - 8: **if** the BMU is a boundary node **then**
 - 9: Grow new neighbouring nodes in all possible directions and evenly redistribute the geographic weights.
 - 10: **else**
 - 11: Increase the error of the neighbouring nodes by the factor of distribution γ and set the error of the BMU to $GT/2$.
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
-

3.2.4. Geographic Smoothing Phase

Finally, to minimise the geographic quantisation error and to force each neuron to learn a representative location, a geographic smoothing phase is conducted. It consists of hierarchically searching for the BMU in the neuron grid learned in the two previous phases and adapting the geographic components of the BMU weight vectors only. The formal weight adaption formula

for some input data point \vec{p}_j can be written as in Eq. 6 where $\delta_{i,\text{BMU}}$ is 1 if $i = \text{BMU}$ and 0 otherwise.

$$\vec{w}_i^{(\text{geo})} = \vec{w}_i^{(\text{geo})} + \alpha^{(\tau)} \cdot \delta_{i,\text{BMU}} \cdot (\vec{p}_j^{(\text{geo})} - \vec{w}_i^{(\text{geo})}) \quad (6)$$

The full training procedure of the Geo-GSOM is finally summarised in Alg. 2.

3.2.5. Implementation Details

After initialisation, G growing iterations, S non-geographic smoothing iterations and S' geographic smoothing iterations are performed by the Geo-GSOM algorithm. During experimentation, a low number of growing iterations (e.g. $G = 10$), a large number of non-geographic smoothing iterations (e.g. $S = 100$), and a low number of geographic smoothing iterations (e.g. $S' = 10$) turned out to produce the best trade-off between speed and cluster quality. The default values for the initial learning rate and neighbourhood radius are $\alpha^{(0)} = 0.3$ and $r^{(0)} = 6$. To speed up learning for very large data sets consisting of tens of thousands or even millions of posts, a batch training procedure can be used instead of iterating over the full data set. In that case, the weights are adapted based on a random batch of fixed size during each growing and smoothing iteration.

3.3. Information Extraction

From each cluster of feature vectors and the respective underlying posts, the top k most important words are extracted along with a summarising cluster label, the cluster sentiment as well as spatial and temporal statistics.

3.3.1. Semantic Topic

To obtain information about the semantic content in the posts of each cluster, the top k keywords are extracted using word importances computed using a term frequency and inverse document frequency (tf-idf) procedure (Salton, 1989). It works as follows:

1. Based on all input documents d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n , the vocabulary and the respective inverse document frequency (idf) values are learned.
2. For each cluster, all contained documents are concatenated and the tf-idf value is calculated using the term frequencies of the learned vocabulary words in the cluster and the learned idf values.

Algorithm 2 Geo-GSOM training procedure

Require: input patterns $\vec{p}_1, \dots, \vec{p}_n \in \mathbb{R}^d$, spread parameters SF and c , initial learning rate $\alpha^{(0)}$, initial neighborhood radius $r^{(0)}$, #growing iterations G , #non-geographic smoothing iterations S , #geographic smoothing iterations S' , geographic tolerance $r_{\text{geo}}, \gamma, x_{\text{max}}, y_{\text{max}}$

1: INITIALISATION PHASE

2: Start with four neurons, initialise the non-geographic weights randomly and assign geographic weights such that they represent the spatial value range.

3: Compute the growth threshold $GT = -D \cdot \ln(SF) \cdot \frac{n}{c}$.

4: GROWING PHASE

5: **for** $\tau = 1$ to G **do**

6: Perform the Geo-GSOM growing algorithm (Alg. 1), i.e. go over all data points, hierarchically search for the BMU, adapt its non-geographic weights, accumulate the error and grow new nodes if needed.

7: In case new nodes are grown, redistribute the geographic weights evenly over the neuron grid.

8: Update neighborhood radius $r^{(\tau)}$ and learning rate $\alpha^{(\tau)}$.

9: **end for**

10: NON-GEOGRAPHIC SMOOTHING PHASE

11: **for** $\tau = 1$ to S **do**

12: Perform the same weight adaption procedure as in the growing phase but do not grow new nodes.

13: **end for**

14: GEOGRAPHIC SMOOTHING PHASE

15: **for** $\tau = 1$ to S' **do**

16: Go over all data points, hierarchically search for the BMU using the learned neuron grid from the previous phases and adapt its geographic weights.

17: **end for**

More formally, Eq. 7 is used to compute weights for each word in a cluster. $\text{tf}_{\text{term,cluster}}$ is the term frequency of a word in all documents of a cluster, n the total number of documents, and $\text{df}_{\text{term}}^{(o)}$ is the number of original documents (posts) containing the term. One is added to the idf such that terms that occur in all documents are not completely ignored and one is also added to

the numerator and denominator of the idf equation to prevent divisions by zero.

$$\text{tf-idf}_{\text{term,cluster}} = \text{tf}_{\text{term,cluster}} \cdot \log \left(\frac{1 + n}{1 + \text{df}_{\text{term}}^{(o)}} \right) + 1 \quad (7)$$

Before word weights are computed, each input text goes through a pipeline of (1) lowercasing, (2) removing special characters, non-character tokens, and links (3) removing user references and (4) converting tags to standalone words to achieve a normalised representation. To reduce the occurrences of uninformative words in the final result, stopwords are ignored when building the vocabulary for the tf-idf calculation. Rare words that occur only in very few documents with document frequency $< \text{df}_{\text{min}}$ and very frequent words with document frequency $> \text{df}_{\text{max}}$ are ignored as well. The two thresholds are parameters of the keyword extraction algorithm. Overall, for each cluster, the top k most important words (keywords) are extracted by computing tf-idf weights for each word and taking the k words with the highest respective values.

The keyword extraction procedure makes the outputs of our model comparable to other topic modelling approaches and specifically allows for the computation of automated topic coherence measures like variants of the Pointwise Mutual Information (PMI) (Jurafsky and Martin, 2023) or topic diversity (Dieng et al., 2020). However, it still operates under the bag-of-words hypothesis and might not be able to capture internal relations between words describing a topic. For this reason, we implemented an additional semantic representation using cluster labels computed by a generative Large Language Model (LLM).

3.3.2. Cluster Label

Although the keyword representation of topics has been the standard for topic modelling for decades (dating back to Deerwester et al., 1990), it ignores the context of words and often requires a fair amount of brainwork to interpret their meaning by humans. Lau et al. (2014) illustrated this issue with two topics learnt from news articles: (1) *farmers, farm, food, rice, agriculture* and (2) *stories, undated, receive, scheduled, clients*. While the first topic is clearly related to agriculture, the theme of the second topic is less clear and might confuse end users, especially those who are not familiar with the underlying corpus of documents.

For this reason, LLMs such as the Generative Pretrained Transformer (GPT) model (Radford et al., 2021; OpenAI, 2023) have been increasingly used to generate concise, understandable topic labels (e.g. Pham et al., 2023). Such a technique was also implemented for the JSTTS model with the help of the Llama-2-70b-chat model (Touvron et al., 2023). After keyword extraction, the keywords and documents of each cluster (or a sample) are used to engineer a prompt that asks the generative LLM to compute a concise topic label that summarises the cluster’s semantic content.

3.3.3. Cluster Sentiment

To obtain a sense of the cluster sentiment, the mode of the estimated sentiments of the posts is computed. As a supplementary measure of the sentiment intensity, the mean of the corresponding sentiment probabilities can be calculated. Additionally, it is possible to obtain a sentiment distribution for each cluster by computing the mean probabilities for each of the three classes *negative*, *neutral* and *positive* or a distribution of the hard class assignments.

3.3.4. Cluster Location

The Geo-GSOM was engineered such that the learned neuron grid preserves geographic coherence. Consequently, a meaningful learned location for each cluster can be extracted from the respective weight vectors. To acquire it, the x and y components can be re-scaled back to their original size and transformed back to latitude and longitude using the inverse of the utilised projection. In addition, a bounding geometry such as the convex hull of the data points within each cluster can be used to visualise the cluster’s spatial spread.

3.3.5. Cluster Time

While the Geo-GSOM also learns representative values for the temporal component of the weight vectors, this alone is only useful with a high temporal weight γ as time makes up only one dimension of the feature vector and quickly loses importance over the other features. For this reason, it is recommended to compute the mean and standard deviation of the Unix time of the posts in each cluster. They provide the most consistent estimates of the temporal centre and deviation.

4. Experiments

Due to the innovative nature of this research, no other directly comparable baseline models exist. Thus, the properties of the JSTTS model were evaluated using a multi-step procedure. We first examined the Geo-GSOM for spatial clustering separately to confirm its performance. Second, we investigated the behaviour of the model given different parametrisations. Finally, we evaluated our JSTTS model against a comparable sequential baseline approach across four use case data sets.

4.1. Spatial Clustering

The Geo-GSOM was developed to leverage the advantages of a GSOM while maintaining geographical coherence. Specifically, the learned locations should be meaningfully distributed in space and the learned neuron grid should preserve spatial neighbourhoods. To show that these properties hold, an experimental study using a manually generated data set of 400 artificial data points was conducted. The generation was implemented in analogy to Bação et al. (2004) who used the same 2D surface grid and threshold values but only 200 data points in total.

4.1.1. Setup

The input data set was generated manually by evenly placing points on a 2D surface with coordinate values $x \in [0, 1]$ and $y \in [0, 2]$. Subsequently, each point in the grid was assigned an additional third attribute value z which depends on the value of y as in Eq. 8 resulting in a valley-like distribution as depicted in Fig. 3.

$$z = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } 0.5 < y < 1.5 \\ 10 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Using the described training data, a regular GSOM and a Geo-GSOM with geographic tolerance $r_{\text{geo}} \in \{0, 2\}$ were trained. The spread parameters were tuned such that the maps grew to approximately 100 nodes so the data set was approximated by a lower number of representative units. All other parameters were kept at their default values as described in Appendix A. To account for the random initialisation of both the GSOM and Geo-GSOM and to provide a more quantitative measure for the coherence of the learned spatial structure, the networks were additionally trained independently 50 times, and for each set of trained units, global Moran’s I was computed. The

Figure 3: The artificial training data generated for the validation of the Geo-GSOM clustering algorithm.

resulting values were averaged to obtain an approximation of the expected Moran’s I .

4.1.2. Results

Fig. 4 shows the learned geographic distribution of the SOM units including the respective z values. The Geo-GSOM learned a uniform and representative geographic distribution of the data as expected. The regular GSOM partly neglected the geographic properties of the data, placing nodes for which $z \approx 10$ in the geographic centre breaking the valley-like structure. In contrast, the trained Geo-GSOM nodes were distributed much more evenly for both values of r_{geo} and the spatial structure, or more concretely, the neighbourhoods present in the training data were better preserved. It is also visible that a low geographic tolerance of $r_{\text{geo}} = 0$ preserved the spatial properties best as the BMU search was conducted purely geographically. In contrast, the learned locations with geographic tolerance $r_{\text{geo}} = 2$ were not spread as evenly, however, the non-geographic components were also considered during the BMU search.

It is further possible to plot the learned neural network structure using a U-matrix-style visualisation of SOMs (Ultsch and Siemon, 1990) as in Fig. 5. The learned neuron structure of the Geo-GSOM was oriented correctly in

Figure 4: Learned weights of the trained (Geo-)GSOM networks in all three dimensions x , y (plotted on the axes) and z (colour) given the artificial training data described in Sec. 4.1.1.

space. The neurons with higher average neighbour distances indicate where the valley in the middle starts and ends as neighbourhood distances are high where the learned z values change significantly. Moreover, it can be observed that the locations of neurons in the grid corresponded to the learned locations for both parametrisations of r_{geo} . In contrast, the orientation, structure and neighbour distances of the standard GSOM neurons did not align at all with the spatial distribution of the original input data or the learned locations.

Figure 5: U-matrix-style representation of the trained (Geo-)GSOM variants. Darker colouring indicates a higher average neighbour distance, though the distances are not equal for the three networks.

To generalise the spatial properties of the Geo-GSOM beyond single train-

ing instances, the achieved Moran’s I values of the learned (Geo-)GSOM weights (averaged over 50 runs) are depicted in Table 1. The Geo-GSOM achieved significantly higher spatial autocorrelation than the GSOM. This indicates that the learned weight vectors were better spatially distributed concerning the z values. The Geo-GSOM with a geographic tolerance of $r_{\text{geo}} = 0$ almost achieved the spatial autocorrelation of the training data and even with $r_{\text{geo}} = 2$, it still largely outperformed the standard GSOM, exhibiting higher values for Moran’s I and much less variance. It is also notable that the learned structure was always exactly the same with $r_{\text{geo}} = 0$ as the BMU search was carried out exclusively geographically, eliminating any effects of randomness.

	r_{geo}	I	$\mathbb{E}[I]$	p	σ_I^2	#nodes
training data	–	0.8602	–0.0025	< 0.01	–	–
GSOM	–	0.4741	–0.0094	< 0.01	0.0148	107.44
Geo-GSOM	0	0.7736	–0.0097	< 0.01	0.0000	104.00
	2	0.5832	–0.0101	< 0.01	0.0011	100.26

Table 1: Global Moran’s I of the learned weight vectors, its expectation, the respective p value under a normality assumption, the variance of σ_I^2 of I and the size of the trained (Geo-)GSOM network averaged over 50 runs.

4.2. Parameter Sensitivity

This section the effects of different feature weights for JSTTS model and illustrates the trade-off between different cluster qualities. The experiments were motivated by the flexibility but also the challenges of the feature engineering process.

4.2.1. Setup

As the JSTTS model was designed specifically for the analysis of social media posts in disaster situations, a tweet data set concerning Hurricane Harvey was used for this evaluation. It is different to the data used in Sec. 5 to provide insights into the model’s performance on different data sets and avoid the overfitting of parameters in the case study.

Hurricane Harvey was a tropical storm that occurred in 2017 and hit the state of Texas in the USA on August 25 (US Department of Commerce, n.d.). The respective data set consists of 28,933 geo-located tweets posted

within the entire area of Texas. It was collected via the former Twitter v1.1 API using the filtered stream and recent search endpoints, filtering by the bounding box Polygon((-98.77 27.58, -90.86 27.58, -90.86 30.66, -98.77 30.66, -98.77 27.58)) and a posting time from August 25 to September 7, 2017.

The JSTTS model was applied to the data using multiple weight configurations. First, each feature weight was set to some value in $\{\frac{1}{10}, \frac{1}{4}, \frac{1}{2}, 1, 2\}$ while keeping the others fixed at $\frac{1}{4}$ to gain an understanding of the model’s behaviour under weight parameter changes. Second, we conducted a grid search in the search space $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in \{\frac{1}{10}, \frac{3}{10}, \frac{5}{10}, \dots, \frac{19}{10}\}$ to confirm the initial observations. The geographic tolerance was set to $r_{\text{geo}} = 2$ for all test runs and the spread parameters to $SF = 0.7$ and $c = 100$. For each of the weight configurations, the following metrics were computed:

- C : the number of output clusters,
- Sentiment Uniformity (SU): the fraction of sentiment labels that align with the global cluster sentiment label,
- Sentiment Intensity (SI): the mean of the probabilities of the cluster sentiment,
- σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 : the average spatial variance of the posts within the clusters in both dimensions of the normalised coordinate space (x and y),
- Topic Quality (TQ) based on the top 10 keywords calculated as the product of Topic Coherence (TC) measured by the positive normalised pointwise mutual information (Bouma, 2009; Jurafsky and Martin, 2023) and Topic Diversity (TD) as defined by Dieng et al. (2020),
- σ_t^2 : the average variance of the normalised posting time within each cluster.

For all runs of our experiments, we used the English-language all-MiniLM-L12-v2 SBERT model (Reimers and Gurevych, 2019) for semantic embedding generation and the twitter-RoBERTa-base-sentiment model (Loureiro et al., 2022) for sentiment classification. Coordinates were projected using the ESRI:102005 equidistant map projection for North America. As a remark, the extent of the bounding box used for the filtering of tweets is significantly wider than high because a large portion of the covered area consists of water from the Gulf of Mexico. Therefore, the variance along the y -axis is expected to be smaller than along the x -axis.

4.2.2. Results

The effects of different sentiment weights while keeping the others fixed are depicted in Table 2. A higher sentiment weight β led to clusters that were more uniform in terms of their sentiment. The average sentiment intensity increased slightly with higher sentiment weights, peaked at $\beta = \frac{1}{2}$, and then decreased again minimally. Higher sentiment weights also yielded more clusters indicating that they became more granular. Topic quality decreased with higher sentiment weights whereas coordinate and time variance increased. Thus, there was a trade-off between sentiment uniformity and intensity and the other cluster qualities.

β	C	SU	SI	TQ	σ_x^2	σ_y^2	σ_t^2
$\frac{1}{10}$	42.200	0.856	0.709	0.197	0.023	0.003	0.059
$\frac{1}{4}$	46.200	0.904	0.755	0.182	0.027	0.003	0.061
$\frac{1}{2}$	46.000	0.958	0.784	0.178	0.027	0.003	0.061
1	53.000	0.967	0.781	0.156	0.029	0.003	0.063
2	60.600	0.976	0.772	0.126	0.031	0.004	0.066

Table 2: Quantitative cluster quality metrics with different sentiment weights β averaged over 5 runs. The best scores are marked in bold. Coordinates and time are normalised.

Table 3 shows the effects of different coordinate weights α while keeping the others fixed. With higher coordinate weights, the average coordinate variance of the clusters decreased. The number of predicted clusters stayed approximately the same with increasing values for α . Notably, topic quality slightly improved. Sentiment uniformity and sentiment intensity decreased marginally and the temporal variance increased. Therefore, more local clusters came with a minimal trade-off for the other cluster qualities.

Regarding the temporal weight γ , the results of different configurations while keeping the other weights fixed are depicted in Table 4. A higher temporal weight led to a lower temporal variance within the clusters, implying that the clusters were more concentrated on the timeline. The number of output clusters stayed approximately the same with larger values for γ . Topic quality, sentiment uniformity, and sentiment intensity decreased, and coordinate variance slightly increased.

To confirm these observations in a more generalised setting, we evaluated

α	C	SU	SI	TQ	σ_x^2	σ_y^2	σ_t^2
$\frac{1}{10}$	42.200	0.927	0.764	0.186	0.030	0.003	0.057
$\frac{1}{4}$	41.600	0.930	0.764	0.192	0.025	0.003	0.061
$\frac{1}{2}$	42.000	0.906	0.748	0.196	0.017	0.003	0.065
1	44.000	0.898	0.750	0.198	0.006	0.002	0.063
2	43.800	0.866	0.727	0.195	0.002	0.001	0.065

Table 3: Quantitative cluster quality metrics with different coordinate weights α averaged over 5 runs. The minimum coordinate variances are marked in bold. Coordinates and time are normalised.

γ	C	SU	SI	TQ	σ_x^2	σ_y^2	σ_t^2
$\frac{1}{10}$	45.200	0.912	0.754	0.197	0.025	0.003	0.062
$\frac{1}{4}$	42.800	0.902	0.755	0.187	0.024	0.003	0.058
$\frac{1}{2}$	44.600	0.892	0.743	0.176	0.025	0.003	0.043
1	45.000	0.891	0.749	0.147	0.032	0.004	0.016
2	46.200	0.844	0.720	0.124	0.038	0.004	0.007

Table 4: Quantitative cluster quality metrics with different temporal weights γ averaged over 5 runs. The minimum temporal variance is marked in bold. Coordinates and time are normalised.

the outputs of our grid search. Because the grid search was conducted in three dimensions α, β, γ with multiple evaluation metrics for each parameter configuration, the initial outputs were highly multi-dimensional and not easily interpretable. We therefore focused on the behavioural properties discovered in the initial experimental setting with fixed parameters. The results are visible in Fig. 6. Each boxplot visualises the range of the respective metric over all possible weight configurations given one fixed parameter represented by the column.

With higher values of β , SU consistently increased and the Pearson correlation over all configurations was 0.831. Consequently, the uniformity of sentiments can be effectively controlled with the sentiment weight β , even if the other weight parameters were also high. Similar observations could be made for the coordinate weight α in both dimensions x and y . Here, the Pearson correlation was -0.918 and -0.835 . In other words, the higher the value of α , the lower the spatial variance. This effect was especially pronounced for dimension x where the value range notably decreased with higher coordinates weights. The same effect was visible for the temporal weight γ and the temporal variance, yielding a negative correlation of -0.947 . Higher values of γ therefore led to clusters that were more concentrated in time. It was therefore possible effectively to control SU, spatial variance and temporal variance using the feature weights. However, it must be noted that the average TQ decreased with higher weights for α, β, γ .

Figure 6: Comparison of feature weights and associated cluster quality metrics. Each boxplot represents all possible parameter configurations for different values of α, β or γ as indicated by the column. Each output metric was averaged over 5 runs (indicated by the bar above the y-axis label). Coordinates and time are normalised.

Overall, the results of this section show that the model parameters α , β and γ allow the user to control the sentiment, spatial, and temporal concentration of the clusters with a trade-off for other qualities. Nonetheless, even given this sensitivity analysis, the parametrisation of the JSTTS remains complex due to the adversarial effects of parameter changes in multiple dimensions.

4.3. Comparative Evaluation

Although no previous method is directly comparable to our JSTTS approach, similar multimodal analyses of geo-social media data have been conducted in the past (e.g. AlAgha, 2021; Kwon et al., 2023; Li et al., 2022) using sequential workflows where each processing step is executed independently. To provide a perspective on how the JSTTS model performs relative to such an independent sequential methodology, we conducted a quantitative evaluation using geo-referenced tweets from four disasters around the world.

4.3.1. Setup

Fig. 7 depicts a visual overview of the experimental setup used to compare the JSTTS model against a state-of-the-art independent sequential analysis workflow. The goal of this evaluation was to assess the model’s quantitative performance and its ability to produce comparable clusters of geo-social media posts across diverse scenarios.

Figure 7: Visual overview of the comparative evaluation. The JSTTS model is compared against a state-of-the-art independent sequential analysis workflow on the basis of four use case data sets and evaluation metrics in all modalities.

To ensure a robust comparison, we applied both methods to four distinct use case data sets: (1) the 2014 Napa earthquake (Brocher et al., 2015), (2) Hurricane Harvey from 2017 (US Department of Commerce, n.d.), (3) the 2021 Ahr Valley flood (Koks et al., 2021) and (4) the 2023 Chile wildfires (Cordero et al., 2024). The data sets were collected using Twitter’s former v1.1 streaming and recent search API endpoints while filtering for posting time and location as depicted in Table 5. The table additionally shows the number of posts, the temporal extent and the total area covered by the bounding box.

Data set	#posts	Time frame	Temporal range	Geographic bounds	Cover area
Ahr Valley floods	11,177	2021-07-01 – 2021-07-31	31 days	(50.01, 6.00, 50.75, 8.00)	1,256 km ²
Hurricane Harvey	28,933	2017-08-25 – 2017-09-07	14 days	(27.58, -98.77, 30.66, -90.86)	26,736 km ²
Chile wildfires	100,707	2023-02-01 – 2023-02-28	28 days	(-55.95, -76.89, -17.34, -65.22)	546,905 km ²
Napa earthquake	90,907	2014-08-24 – 2014-08-25	1 day	(37.11, -123.05, 38.98, -121.04)	4,287 km ²

Table 5: Properties of the data sets used for the comparative evaluation. The time frame and geographic bounds were used for filtering. In addition, we computed the number of posts within each data set, the temporal range and the size of the cover area.

Our JSTTS model was configured using the feature weights $\alpha = \frac{3}{2}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\gamma = \frac{1}{4}$ based on the findings of Sec. 4.2. Time was given a low weight as the data sets were already filtered by posting time. The Geo-GSOM was parametrised with $SF = 0.85$ and $c = 150$ as this setting yielded 54 to 91

clusters for all test data sets, ensuring that the clusters were fine-grained enough to capture localised patterns in the data while avoiding excessive over-segmentation. For the 2014 Napa earthquake and 2017 Hurricane Harvey data, we used the English-only all-MiniLM-L12-v2 SBERT model for embedding generation and twitter-RoBERTa-base-sentiment for sentiment classification. Conversely, we used the multilingual counterparts distiluse-base-multilingual-cased-v1 and twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-base-sentiment for the 2021 Ahr Valley flood and the 2023 Chile wildfires. The utilised coordinate projections were ESRI:102031 for Europe, ESRI:102005 for North America and ESRI:102032 for South America. For all remaining parameters, the default values as described in Appendix A were used.

The alternative sequential workflow follows a pipeline of (1) sentiment analysis, (2) topic modelling and (3) spatial clustering. First, sentiment analysis and topic modelling are conducted independently. Second, the posts within each topic are clustered in geographic space to achieve outputs comparable to our JSTTS results. For sentiment analysis, we used twitter-RoBERTa-base-sentiment and twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-base-sentiment as in the JSTTS setup. Topic modelling was conducted with BERTopic (Grotenborst, 2022) using the MiniLM-L12-v2 and distiluse-base-multilingual-cased-v1 embedding models, respectively. We utilised k -means during the BERTopic application instead of the default HDBSCAN algorithm to ensure that every post is assigned to a topic. The posts within each topic were subsequently clustered again using k -means on the normalised x and y coordinates of the posts. Time was disregarded in this workflow as the data sets were already filtered temporally to avoid additional clustering hierarchies.

To ensure similar outputs, we first applied the JSTTS model and subsequently approximated the resulting number of clusters using factorisation for the independent sequential approach. In the process, we allowed for a maximum of six spatial clusters within each topic. Finally, we computed the following metrics each of the final outputs:

- $\bar{\text{size}}$: average cluster size,
- σ_{size} : standard deviation in cluster size,
- TQ: the overall topic quality calculated as the product of TC measured by the positive normalised pointwise mutual information (Bouma, 2009; Jurafsky and Martin, 2023) and TD as defined by Dieng et al. (2020) based on the top 10 keywords,

- SU: the fraction of sentiment labels aligning with the global cluster sentiment label,
- σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 : the average spatial variance of the posts within the clusters in both dimensions of the normalised coordinate space (x and y),
- σ_t^2 : the average variance of the normalised posting time within each cluster.

4.3.2. Results

Table 6 shows the number of clusters generated by the JSTTS approach alongside the corresponding numbers from the sequential workflow for each data set. It also provides a breakdown of the sequential workflow into (1) the number of semantic topics and (2) spatial clusters per topic which indicate the total number of clusters when multiplied. For the Ahr Valley data, one of the topic clusters only contained two distinct locations, resulting in two instead of six spatial clusters for that topic. Thus, 86 clusters were identified instead of the intended 90.

Data	JSTTS clusters	Sequential clusters	<i>Sequential topics</i>	<i>Sequential spatial clusters</i>
Ahr Valley floods	91	86	15	6
Hurricane Harvey	84	84	14	6
Chile wildfires	54	54	9	6
Napa earthquake	85	85	17	5

Table 6: Breakdown of the number of output clusters from both the JSTTS approach and the sequential workflow. The sequential clusters are computed by first identifying a pre-defined number of topics and subsequently clustering the data points within each topic spatially. The total number of sequential clusters is therefore *topics * spatial clusters*.

Table 7 summarises the evaluation metrics for all outputs. For both methods, the average cluster size increased naturally with the size of the input data, ranging from 122.8 posts for the Ahr Valley data set (11,177

posts) to 1,864.9 posts for the Chile wildfires data set (100,707 posts). Across all data sets, the average relative cluster size was consistent at 1.3% of the total input size for both methods. However, the standard deviation of cluster sizes was generally lower for the JSTTS approach, indicating slightly more balanced clustering. For instance, for the Ahr Valley data set, the JSTTS approach produced only one cluster with fewer than five posts, whereas the sequential workflow generated 16 such clusters.

	Ahr Valley floods		Hurricane Harvey		Chile wildfires		Napa earthquake	
	JSTTS	Seq.	JSTTS	Seq.	JSTTS	Seq.	JSTTS	Seq.
$\bar{\text{size}}$	122.8	130.0	344.4	344.4	1,864.9	1,864.9	1,069.5	1,069.5
σ_{size}	181.2	223.3	739.3	817.3	3,146.8	4,220.1	1,024.2	1,191.8
TQ	0.165	0.029	0.191	0.042	0.142	0.034	0.081	0.030
SU	0.891	0.81	0.926	0.832	0.837	0.673	0.894	0.603
σ_x^2	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.003	0.004
σ_y^2	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.002	0.004	0.004
σ_t^2	0.067	0.065	0.056	0.061	0.002	0.002	0.076	0.067

Table 7: Evaluation metrics for the outputs produced by our JSTTS approach and the independent sequential workflow (Seq.) across four use case data sets. The metrics include the average cluster size, the standard deviation among the cluster sizes σ_{size} , the semantic topic quality TQ measured as the product of coherence and diversity, the sentiment uniformity SU, the variance among the normalised spatial coordinates σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 and the variance of the normalised time σ_t^2 . The best scores are marked in bold.

TQ was consistently higher for the JSTTS model across all data sets, often by several margins. This is caused by the fact that the sequential workflow relies on spatial sub-clustering within each topic cluster which introduces semantic redundancy. Breaking up the TQ score, the average TD was 0.49 for the JSTTS approach while it was only 0.11 for the sequential method. In terms of TC, the two methods scored similarly. The JSTTS approach yielded an average value of 0.31 while the independent sequential workflow yielded an average TC of 0.33.

SU was also higher for the JSTTS approach across the board, frequently reaching values close to 0.9. The lowest SU score (0.837) was achieved for the Chile wildfire data set which was still higher than the sequential workflow’s maximum SU of 0.832 for Hurricane Harvey. The respective minimum SU

was 0.603 for the Napa earthquake data. Over all data sets, the average SU was 0.89 for the JSTTS model and 0.73 for the sequential workflow. Consequently, the clusters were more sentimentally uniform for the JSTTS model. Nevertheless, the sequential approach also produced clusters with sentimentally consistent posts, albeit less reliably.

For spatial variance (σ_x^2 and σ_y^2), the two approaches performed comparably, with minor differences across specific data sets. No consistent advantage was observed for either method. The same holds for the temporal variance σ_t^2 . While the sequential workflow yielded a lower temporal variance for the Ahr Valley and Napa earthquake data, it was on par with the JSTTS method for the Chile wildfires and higher for Hurricane Harvey. The spatial and temporal variance of the two methods can thus be regarded as similar.

In summary, the JSTTS model produced clusters with higher semantic quality and more uniform sentiment while maintaining spatial and temporal characteristics comparable to the sequential workflow. These findings highlight the JSTTS model’s capacity to improve clustering outcomes without sacrificing spatial or temporal coherence.

Additionally, the comparative experiments emphasise the generalisability of the JSTTS model across data sets with varying sizes, geographic extents and temporal spans. The mean relative spatial extent of the clusters, measured as the ratio of the average cluster cover area to the full data set’s cover area, was 7.4%, ranging from 3.9% to 13.1%. Similarly, the mean relative temporal extent was 25.9%, ranging from 22.1% to 29.1%. These results demonstrate the JSTTS model’s adaptability to the spatial and temporal characteristics of diverse data sets.

5. Case Study

A major motivation for the JSTTS model design was to make the results interpretable for real-world use cases. Therefore, in addition to the experiments in Sec. 4, a case study was conducted to demonstrate the model’s capabilities in a disaster management setting. As input data, the 2021 Ahr Valley flood in Western Germany was considered. From July 14 to 15, 2021, heavy rainfall hit the region causing a major flood, severe structural and economic damage as well as human casualties (Bundesministerium des Innern und für Heimat, 2022; Koks et al., 2021). To analyse the response to the catastrophe via social media, we used the 11,177 tweets posted within the Ahr Valley region in Germany and surroundings in July 2021 from Sec. 4.3.

They were obtained via the former Twitter v1.1 API using the filtered stream and recent search endpoints. The tweets were filtered using the bounding box Polygon((6.00 50.01, 8.00 50.01, 8.00 50.75, 6.00 50.75, 6.00 50.01)) and the month of July as the time frame. The resulting data set consists of tweets in multiple languages, mainly German, English and Dutch. This case study therefore also addresses the model’s handling of multilingual data - which has been a major challenge in previous topic modelling approaches, particularly for bag-of-words-based methods such as LDA. Specifically, the multilingual distiluse-base-multilingual-cased-v1 SBERT model (Reimers and Gurevych, 2020) was used for semantic embedding generation and the twitter-XLM-RoBERTa-base-sentiment model (Barbieri et al., 2022) for sentiment classification. Coordinates were projected using the equidistant ESRI:102031 map projection for Europe. The validation of the JSTTS model using a real-world case study was also strongly motivated by the conclusion of Hoyle et al. (2022, p. 5358) regarding topic model evaluation stating that “[...] topic models - indeed, of all NLP models - should be done with use cases firmly in mind.”

5.1. Setup

For the case study, a configuration identical to Sec. 4.3 was used because it could effectively identify geographically local clusters with high semantic and sentiment coherence. The coordinate weight was set to $\alpha = \frac{3}{2}$ to enforce a low spatial variance, the sentiment weight was set to $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$ based on the results of Sec. 4.2 and the temporal weight was set to $\gamma = \frac{1}{4}$ as the data had already been pre-filtered temporally. Furthermore, the Geo-GSOM was parametrised with $SF = 0.85$ and $c = 150$ as this configuration was proven to be effective in Sec. 4.3.

5.2. Results

The initial output consisted of 91 clusters. Subsequently, the clusters that might be concerned with the flood, were identified by filtering for the keywords ”hochwasser”, ”flut”, ”flood”, ”hilfe”, ”notfall”. After this filtering process, 13 clusters consisting of 1,592 tweets remained.

For each of those clusters, multimodal information was extracted using the workflow described in Sec. 3.3. A visualisation of the cluster labels, sentiments, cluster locations and spatial spread is depicted in Fig. 8. Representative cluster locations were obtained from the feature vectors learned by the Geo-GSOM, labels were computed using Llama-2-70b-chat, cluster sentiments were obtained using the mode and the spatial spread is indicated

by the convex hull of the underlying posts. To add contextual information, the map was enriched with a heat map of the posts within each cluster and also displays the flooded areas identified by the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (Copernicus Emergency Management Service, 2021). All filtered clusters overlapped with at least one flooded area. Exemplary mappings of cluster keywords and tweets to labels are depicted in Table 8. The full set of relevant output clusters can be summarised as follows:

- Cluster 8 was overall neutral in sentiment and contained topics such as emergency services, weather conditions, and regional events.
- Cluster 13 was also neutral and comprised of posts mentioning French, adventure and local concerns.
- Cluster 14 was negatively connoted and discussed issues like soliciting assistance regarding the Ahr Valley flood and dog-related problems.
- Cluster 27 was also negatively associated and highlighted challenges faced in the Ahr Valley region, including water-related troubles and power outages.
- Cluster 38 was another predominantly negative collection of posts which mentioned government, illness and the aftermath of flooding in the Ahr Valley.
- Cluster 39 mentioned locations and Finnish words in a neutral context.
- Cluster 54 mostly discussed local concerns neutrally.
- Cluster 55 was another neutral cluster and mentioned topics like leverage, redemption and Christian Kane.
- Cluster 71 was neutrally connoted as well and highlighted locations and activities such as basketball camps.
- Cluster 74 was negatively associated and expressed concerns about the impacts and aftermath of the flood disaster.
- Cluster 76 was another negative cluster that was strongly concerned with the flood.
- Cluster 82 mostly discussed local happenings in a neutral context.
- Lastly, cluster 87 also remained neutral and included weather-related posts from Belgium.

Figure 8: Visual representation of the multimodal Ahr Valley clusters identified as potentially flood-related, juxtaposed with respect to the associated sentiment (negative and neutral). The figure displays the convex hull of the clusters in geographic space, coloured by sentiment. The cluster labels in the format *cluster ID:name* were computed with the help of Llama-2-70b-chat and placed at the representative cluster location learned by the Geo-GSOM. The density of underlying posts is displayed using a heat map. To provide context, flooded areas identified by the Copernicus Emergency Management Service are depicted in blue.

ID	Top 15 key-words	Exemplary tweets	Cluster label
38	ahrweiler, menschen, regierung, nena, erkrankung, hochwasser, ahrtal, jahren, personen, home, einzig, macht, people, schützen, impfung	<p>”Earlier German chancellor promised these victims would not be forgotten. One question we keep hearing from people here, when will official aid arrive?”,</p> <p>”Es gibt z.B. Hochwasserwarnstufen 1-4 aber wenn die zuständigen öffentlichen Stellen nichts tun (schlafen, versagen) wie immer bei solchen Katastrophen ist man hilflos.”,</p> <p>”Es ist wirklich schrecklich was das Hochwasser hinterlassen hat. Eine reine Katastrophe. Wir sind sprachlos von der riesigen Spendenaktion und der großen Hilfsbereitschaft. Vielen Dank an Alle. Folgt uns gerne mal auf Twitter.”</p>	Flood Disaster and Government Criticism
76	unwetter, halt, laschet, grade, hochwasser, hunger, since, bomm, möchte, wetter, stadt, wasser, richtig, leider, tierheim	<p>”Got called at 3 am in the morning. Luckily the water is getting pumped out by firefighters! Unfortunately, the whole street was flooded - which is why they had to work at night too. A visiting old lady also lost her car in the underground garage. The flood came way too quick.”,</p> <p>”Dass die Nachrichten nach dem #Unwetter immer noch schlimmer werden, hätte ich nicht gedacht... Soviele Tote und Zerstörung ...”,</p> <p>”RIP washing machines. One car was trapped inside the underground garage when it started flooding....I couldn’t find my gummi boots and it was very dark in the basement. It was a great mistake...”</p>	Weather Disasters & Everyday Struggles

Table 8: Exemplary labels computed from the cluster keywords and a sample of the underlying tweets.

Notably, clusters 27, 74 and 76 could be directly identified as collections of flood-related posts that contained relevant in-situ information that is useful for emergency responders. Moreover, cluster 38 provided insights into public opinion about government actions and the quality of disaster management.

The distribution of sentiments within each cluster is depicted in Table 9.

Except for clusters 39 and 54, which were concerned with topics beyond the flood, the uniformity of sentiments was always greater than 87%.

Figure 9: Number of posts per sentiment within each cluster. The highest uniformity was achieved by clusters 8, 71, 76 and 87 of which all posts were of the same sentiment. Conversely, cluster 54 was the least sentimentally uniform cluster where only 59% of posts had the same sentiment.

Despite the multimodal nature of the clusters, the temporal context of each one is of central importance for interpreting the clusters' meaning. Table 9 depicts the temporal mean of the posts in each cluster and the temporal standard deviation to distinguish rapidly emerging or vanishing clusters from more continuous ones. In addition, Fig. 10 and 11 show the spatio-temporal unfolding of the clusters. We computed the number of posts within each cluster per day and the convex hull for each week of July. It can be observed that clusters more concerned with general topics like weather conditions and local events, that is, 8, 39, 54, 55, 82 and 87 had their temporal mean just around July 15 or slightly earlier. The posts were distributed fairly evenly over the entire month of July and almost exclusively neutrally connoted. Their geographic extent stayed approximately the same over time. On the contrary, clusters 13, 14, 27, 38, 71, 74 and 76 grew significantly in the number of daily

posts and their geographic extent after the occurrence of the flood. They discussed the impact and the aftermath of the flood more directly. Moreover, they had their temporal mean a few days after the flood or on the day of the flood and were mostly associated with negative sentiment. This temporal interpretation can therefore be leveraged to gain insights during different stages of the disaster.

Figure 10: Number of tweets posted per day in each of the clusters throughout July 2021.

Finally, we interpreted the neuron grid learned by the Geo-GSOM which is visualised in Figure 12. The grid represents the region covered by the input data and the position of all clusters on the grid. It can therefore also be used to identify the clusters of disaster-related posts in geographic space and for further interpretation. For instance, the average neighbour distances at the centre of the map, which represents the region along the Rhine River, are higher than the average neighbour distances at the edge of the map. This is in line with the fact that tweet density was significantly higher in these regions.

This exemplary study demonstrates the practical usefulness of the JSTTS model for identifying clusters of disaster-related posts in a real-world scenario. The computed clusters are geographically limited and can be examined

ID	Label	Size	\bar{t}	σ_t
8	Cochem, Germany: Weather, Sights, & Events	37	2021-07-15 20:50	10 days, 02h 52m
13	Eifel Region Experiences Severe Flooding	17	2021-07-19 06:04	6 days, 04h 10m
14	Tweets about Tom Hiddleston and current events	74	2021-07-16 14:42	6 days, 19h 34m
27	Devastating floods in Germany's Eifel region	27	2021-07-17 02:56	6 days, 16h 19m
38	Flood Disaster and Government Criticism	287	2021-07-20 10:22	6 days, 21h 21m
39	Exploring Germany's scenic towns	118	2021-07-13 22:57	7 days, 09h 46m
54	Scenic Rurberg and surrounding areas	78	2021-07-15 15:43	9 days, 05h 34m
55	Tweets about Christian Kane and Leverage	254	2021-07-15 16:06	8 days, 15h 32m
71	Basketball camps, Notfallseelsorge, and DRK	31	2021-07-21 20:35	5 days, 20h 11m
74	Flood, destruction, and help	34	2021-07-20 11:01	9 days, 08h 40m
76	Weather Disasters & Everyday Struggles	152	2021-07-15 10:59	8 days, 06h 48m
82	Exploring Bonn, Germany with food, fun, and friends	397	2021-07-15 20:20	8 days, 14h 18m
87	Mixed bag of tweets	86	2021-07-15 11:42	9 days, 07h 32m

Table 9: Temporal statistics of the Ahr Valley clusters including the temporal mean \bar{t} and the temporal standard deviation σ_t .

Figure 11: Convex hulls of the Ahr Valley clusters for each week of July 2021, coloured by the associated sentiment. For each of the plots, only the posts that occurred within the specified time frame were considered for the convex hull computation.

Figure 12: U-matrix-style visualisation of the neuron grid learned by the Geo-GSOM. Darker colouring indicates a higher average neighbour distance, meaning that the learned weight vector is more different to the neighbouring weight vectors.

further by emergency response entities, thus narrowing down the complexity of thousands of social media posts to a dozen relevant local clusters.

6. Discussion

The discussion section of this study is divided into two parts. First, we critically examine the results of the experiments conducted for this research. Second, we discuss the limitations of our work and provide an outlook on future research.

6.1. Discussion of the Results

This study introduced two methodological advancements: The JSTTS model for the multimodal analysis of geo-referenced textual social media posts and the spatially explicit Geo-GSOM learning algorithm for clustering. The JSTTS model provides an effective approach for identifying geographically delineated sentiment-associated semantic clusters in large social media data sets. When evaluated against a comparable sequential analysis workflow, the JSTTS model achieved higher semantic topic quality and sentiment uniformity while maintaining similar levels of spatial and temporal variance. The approach is applicable to arbitrary data sets and works unsupervised. The output is human readable due to the LLM-based label generation mechanism which has not been utilised in comparable research. This presents a major innovation in GI methodology for disaster management as a large, complex collection of data could rapidly be reduced to its most important aspect, allowing for quicker and better decision-making in already exceptional circumstances. It is important to note, however, that traditional or sequential approaches are not necessarily inferior. They offer complementary strengths and may be better suited for answering specific research questions or in scenarios that require greater flexibility over individual analytical components.

In addition, the performance of the Geo-GSOM for spatial clustering was evaluated by comparing it to a standard non-spatial GSOM using artificial training data. The results indicate that the Geo-GSOM was significantly better at preserving spatial coherence during the learning process. We furthermore conducted a sensitivity analysis of the feature weight parameters. It could be observed that the uniformity of sentiments as well as the spatial and temporal concentration could effectively be controlled using the feature

weights α , β and γ . However, their choice is still non-trivial and multiple dimensions of cluster qualities have to be considered when tuning these values. For our case study and experiments related to disaster management, we prioritised spatial and semantic coherence –answering the questions *what* and *where* – based on expert inputs and given that the data had already been filtered temporally. However, depending on the use case, needs might be different, potentially even involving weighting certain dimensions (e.g. negative sentiment) differently than others. For users dealing with time-critical scenarios, we recommend initially using our default parameters $\alpha = \frac{3}{2}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\gamma = \frac{1}{4}$. These settings have been validated to achieve a robust balance across all clustering dimensions throughout our experiments. If additional fine-tuning is required, we suggest incremental adjustments, prioritising the parameter corresponding to the most critical dimension: for instance, increasing α to enhance spatial coherence or γ for higher temporal concentration.

Similarly, the parametrisation of the Geo-GSOM also poses a challenge, especially regarding the growth parameters SF and c . In Sec. 4.3 and 5, we provided a default configuration of $SF = 0.85$ and $c = 150$ which ensured that the clusters were fine-grained enough to capture local patterns while still producing an interpretable overview of the data. Users are advised to start with this configuration and then incrementally adjust the SF parameter. Setting it to a higher value generates more clusters while a lower value produces fewer clusters. For a more drastic adjustment of cluster numbers, the c parameter can also be increased/decreased to produce significantly more/fewer clusters. Regardless, the complex parametrisation remains a major limitation of our approach. This issue is common to many neural networks as the training process is inherently non-deterministic. In this context, recent studies have demonstrated that LLMs can effectively handle complex parameter tuning tasks (Ma et al., 2024). Building upon these findings, subsequent research could explore the use of LLMs to simplify and streamline parameter selection in our approach, thereby reducing complexity and improving usability.

To showcase the real-world utility of our approach, a case study regarding the 2021 Ahr Valley flooding in Germany was conducted. The output of our model provided a granular, locally delineated overview of sentiment-associated topics in different geographic areas with additional temporal insights. It can therefore be used effectively to aid decision-making in disaster management by reducing thousands of social media posts to a single map of local clusters with a readable cluster label, an associated sentiment and

a timestamp. Yet, the outputs can still be improved as we only applied a naive keyword filter to extract the potentially disaster-related clusters. As a result, some of the clusters were not directly relevant for disaster management (e.g. "Tweets about Christian Kane and Leverage") but still occurred in the output because some of the contained posts mentioned the flood. To mitigate this, different techniques of semantic filtering might be explored and integrated in future iterations of our approach.

6.2. Discussion of the Methodology

Due to its component-wise architecture, the JSTTS model can also be modified for input data beyond text. Depending on the concrete use case, additional modalities such as image embeddings, socio-demographic traits or mobility patterns could be included in the feature vectors while others like time could be excluded.

Even though the model was evaluated extensively, the results are nonetheless limited. In Sec. 4.3, we only considered one sequential workflow as a baseline approach. However, its sequential nature would allow for multiple configurations. We chose the variant that produced outputs closest to our JSTTS configuration. The adversarial sequential approach could also be modified further by exploring different clustering and topic modelling algorithms. This optimisation, however, is out of the scope of this research work. Also, the practical usefulness of the methodology was only explicitly verified for disaster management. The transferability to other use cases is subject to supplementary studies.

As already pointed out in Sec. 6.1, the parametrisation of the JSTTS model can be complex. It strongly depends on the desired output and single parameter changes might cause multi-dimensional adversarial effects. Additional research regarding model explainability is therefore desirable. It might be useful to explore the development of an algorithm aimed at optimising the parametrisation of the JSTTS model given information about the desired output. The parametrisation challenge even concerns the dimensionality of the feature space: Since the number of dimensions for semantics, sentiment, space and time differ, each modality contributes an uneven part to the Euclidean distance in multimodal vector space. While it would generally be possible to reduce each modality down to one dimension, this would oversimplify the data, resulting in significantly decreased performance. During the conception of this paper, a one- or two-dimensional semantic representation rapidly diminished the semantic quality of clusters, even with α , β and

γ set to very small numbers. For this reason, we decided to go with five semantic dimensions which is currently the standard choice in topic modelling (Grootendorst, 2022; Angelov, 2020). Similarly, three dimensions can best represent the distribution of sentiments when considering the three *negative*, *neutral* and *positive*. Nonetheless, further research is required to verify the optimal dimensionality of the feature space. In part, α , β and γ were introduced to make up for the unequal number of dimensions during distance computations.

Another constraint of the methodology is that each data point is assigned to exactly one cluster and consequently only one sentiment-associated topic. However, this also eases the readability of the output in the context of disaster management where information should be rapidly interpretable. This behaviour could be changed by considering the distance to the Geo-GSOM units instead of mapping the data points directly, thus achieving a sort of soft clustering. Besides that, the random initialisation of the starting neurons and the stochastic nature of UMAP make the JSTTS model non-deterministic which is also a major caveat of many pure topic modelling approaches (e.g. Blei et al., 2003; Grootendorst, 2022). In case a fixed number of clusters is desired, the Geo-GSOM can either be modified to stop growing when a certain number of neurons are reached or a regular Geo-SOM can be used. The latter option, though, decimates the model’s capabilities to grow a neuron grid that captures the topology of the data. Another direction for further research could therefore be the comparison of the Geo-GSOM algorithm to other clustering algorithms that also consider geographic space. In this context, co-clustering might also be explored as an alternative to traditional cluster analysis (Hubig et al., 2017).

Since a central part of the JSTTS workflow consists of semantic feature vector creation, sentiment classification and label generation, its performance largely depends on the models used for these processing steps. While large pre-trained transformer models such as SBERT, RoBERTa or Llama-2 deliver high quantitative performance, they are computationally expensive and represent a significant bottleneck in terms of runtime and memory requirements. It is therefore difficult to scale the presented JSTTS model to large data sets with hundreds of thousands or millions of data points without a Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) with significant memory. Moreover, UMAP also scales badly for very large data sets (McInnes, n.d.). Although these components can be exchanged with computationally faster techniques, this might involve a trade-off for other qualities. Additionally, the explainabil-

ity of the output is strongly limited. The semantic embedding, sentiment classification and label generation models are essentially used as black boxes with little knowledge of how internal decisions are made. This, however, is a general challenge in computational linguistics (Zini and Awad, 2022).

Lastly, while our proposed JSTTS model demonstrates substantial capabilities in discovering multimodal patterns in social media data, it does not incorporate interconnections between posts or information propagation between users. Rather, the approach takes on a content perspective that considers each post independently. While this view is taken on frequently in social media analysis for disaster management (Saroj and Pal, 2020), it limits the model’s capabilities to capture human interactions and information flows. Future extensions of the JSTTS approach could integrate this information, allowing for more comprehensive and additional insights such as how topics and sentiments spread within the network, where misinformation originates from and what user communities there are. Insights on how this could be achieved are provided by Bai et al. (2024) who merged emotions, semantic topics, spatial coordinates, time and conversational graph structures from social media into an attributed dynamic graph to tackle a likewise challenge for heritage-related events. A similar approach could be taken to extend our JSTTS method. In this context, previous work on modelling information diffusion in online social networks (e.g. Liu et al., 2018; Li et al., 2017; Guille and Hacid, 2012) must also be considered. However, this would require data beyond independent singular posts which was not available in our case. For this reason, it is out of scope for this paper. Still, we highly encourage efforts to integrate this idea in future research.

7. Conclusion

Motivated by applications in geo-social media research and geoinformatics, this study explored the multimodal analysis of social media data, proposing the new JSTTS GeoAI model. It is capable of computing multimodal clusters of posts that are coherent regarding semantics, sentiment, space and time. As part of this endeavour, we introduced the Geo-GSOM, a modified GSOM for spatial clustering. The properties of the JSTTS GeoAI model and the Geo-GSOM were validated and evaluated experimentally. Given artificial training data with a spatial autocorrelation (measured by global Moran’s I) of $I = 0.86$, the neuron grid of the Geo-GSOM maintained spatial autocorrelation values of up to $I = 0.77$ (90%) while a regular non-spatial GSOM

only achieved a spatial autocorrelation of $I = 0.47$ (55%). We also showed that sentiment uniformity, spatial and temporal variance could be effectively be controlled using feature weight parameters. The absolute Pearson correlation between the respective feature weights and evaluation metrics (SU, spatial and temporal variance) ranged from 0.831 to 0.947. Furthermore, the JSTTS model was compared against a similar state-of-the-art sequential approach across several use case data sets where it yielded significantly higher TQ scores with an average value of 0.145 versus 0.034 for the sequential approach. SU was also higher, reaching an average value of 0.89 while the adversarial sequential workflow only yielded a mean value of 0.73. Spatial and temporal variance were similar for both approaches with no consistent differences. The comparative experiments were conducted across four data sets with significant differences in size, spatial extent, temporal range and language. The JSTTS approach generalised well among this data, achieving an average cluster size of 1.3% of the input data size, where each cluster covered an average of 7.4% of the entire study area and ranged across 25.9% of the respective temporal extent.

In a real-world scenario, the JSTTS GeoAI model is able to compute topic-sentiment clusters that are geographically and temporally local. Therefore, information about *where* and *when* people are posting about *what* and how they *feel* about it can be gained. Given a data set of tweets posted in the German Ahr Valley region in July 2021, when a major flood hit the area, the JSTTS GeoAI model provided tangible insights into region-specific posting behaviour on social media. Specifically, our approach was used to identify clusters potentially relevant to emergency responders which contained a multitude of information that could be leveraged to improve aid efforts. The presented model is therefore a powerful tool for gaining a quick overview of the on-site situation via geo-social media analysis. Since the required input is merely a collection of geo- and time-referenced social media posts, the approach can be also used for a variety of other use cases providing a basis for many further research efforts. Examples beyond disaster management where joint spatio-temporal topic-sentiment analysis of social media posts could be useful include spatio-temporal epidemiology, geo-political discourse analysis, large-scale event monitoring or global social network investigations.

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Appendix A. Default Model Parameters

This appendix section contains a brief overview of the JSTTS model parameters including their default values in Table A.10.

Feature Engineering		
Parameter	Description	Default Value
α	coordinate weight	-
β	sentiment weight	-
γ	temporal weight	-
Geo-GSOM		
Parameter	Description	Default value
SF	spread factor	-
c	spread parameter	-
$\alpha^{(0)}$	initial learning rate	0.3
$r^{(0)}$	initial neighbourhood radius	6
G	growing iterations	10
S	non-geographic smoothing iterations	100
S'	geographic smoothing iterations	10
r_{geo}	geographic tolerance	2
γ	factor of (error) distribution	0.1
Information Extraction		
Parameter	Description	Default value
df_{min}	minimum (absolute) document frequency for keyword extraction	10
df_{max}	maximum (relative) document frequency for keyword extraction	0.7

Table A.10: Default parameters for each of the three processing steps of the JSTTS model: (1) feature engineering, (2) clustering with Geo-GSOM and (3) information extraction. The recommended initial configuration for the feature weights is $\alpha = \frac{3}{2}$, $\beta = \frac{1}{3}$ and $\gamma = \frac{1}{4}$. For the spread parameters of the Geo-GSOM, we advise an initial setting of $SF = 0.85$ and $c = 150$. Subsequently, users may incrementally adjust these parameters based on their specific analytical requirements or the desired granularity of clusters.